

GUARANTEE SAFE MOVEMENT BY DESIGNING DRIVER'S WORK MODE THROUGH VEHICLE KEY IN ORGANIZING INTERNATIONAL TRANSPORTATION.

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Annotation. The drivers' activities followed their rest regimes The program is developed and put into the system and the car lock The result was committed through the fault of the drivers the number of accidents is reduced several times).

Keywords: work mode, rest mode, car, car lock, key.

Introduction. Most of the accidents caused by the fault of the driver are due to the consequences of not following the work and rest regimes. When driving this car, the driver is placed in the key of the program based on the mode of work and rest developed by the transport company. As a result, the driver cannot control the car at any time, but the car is driven only based on a certain work and rest program placed in the key, as a result, the number of car accidents is reduced several times [1,2,3]. This key software development issue is very important today.

Relevance of the topic. The goal is to create normal conditions for drivers, to ensure that this schedule is automatically fulfilled by developing a normal work and rest mode. Today, 20-30 percent of car accidents occur due to non-compliance with this regime [4,5,6,7,8]. It is true that in international transportation, the driver's working mode is handled by the tachograph. The transportation process is organized through this equipment in Europe and Russia, and the control of the driver's work and rest mode is organized based on strict instructions, and this method has become widespread. But even in this method, the elimination of violations is mainly given to the driver. A fine is imposed on those who violate the rules [9,10,11,12,13].

Result. With a different approach to this issue, if a system program for drivers is developed and managed based on it [14], if the driver's key is included as a system element among the participants of this system, and the driver's work and rest mode are placed in the Online system, the problem will be solved. The system elements are the immobilizer and the ignition key, which are automatically controlled from the central control point by means of a software control system. When the automatic control system command is received based on the program, if the lock and key match according to the instructions, the system will start and the car will move. Commanding the elements with a walking pass will prevent the lock from opening if the lock and key don't match. As a result, the motor vehicle voluntarily submits to the command according to the mode [15,16]. We have developed an effective program for them to use this system, and through the Oline system, information will be sent to the lock

(lock) and the key (lock). If the code elements match, the car will continue to run. This situation is managed according to the schedule of work and rest of the drivers in Figure 1. In this process, the driver is basically completely controlled from small rest to big rest. Even if the driver wants to work more, the system does not allow him. In this case, it depends on the approved graph of the driver's activity controller, shift 1 and 2 and placing it in the system memory via OnLine [17,18,19].

Figure 1. Schedule of work and rest mode for drivers at various distances, in a meeting or service A schedule is developed to organize the work and rest of the drivers on the basis of the driver's rest-work schedule in the driver's participation at different distances, in the assembly or service, at the driver's exchange places. When creating the graph, the main focus is on whether the car is new or old, the number of shifts per day, and the graph is viable and effective for ensuring the safety of the driver's movement [20]. The main focus is to get high results by making and using the graph correctly. It is a program for configured graphics drivers [23,24]. When creating a schedule, great attention is paid to the driver's rest and work mode, as a result, the difference between previous schedules and the tachograph method in Europe is that an effective schedule for the process is strictly followed. In daily operation, the mode is executed, if there is an error, the key is automatically excluded from opening the lock in the system through OnLine [21,22]. As a result, the 2nd driver takes the place of the working driver through the influence of the driver's work and rest schedule.

Figure 2. Opening and closing the car lock

In the implementation of this work, information is received in the lock zone through the OnLine system. This situation is shown in Figure 2. Opening and closing the car lock is done through the driver's door. The main task for the car is to maintain the driver's work and rest schedule, eliminate the driver's violation of the regime and reduce the number of accidents.

For this, a driver's schedule of work and rest is developed [25]. Based on this schedule of work and rest, the car moves. As a result, the system is based on the plan with the capture of the mode movement is performed, otherwise without unlocking the car the walk stops, the car is freed from steering in the event of fatigue that interferes with it. When a car equipped with the OnLine device is put into operation, the approved study driver's work and rest plan is connected via the OnLine device. The lock is opened for the driver. In this way, it is ensured that all the vehicles in the transport are awake according to the schedule of work and rest.

Conclusion, The legal process of drivers in the car is monitored electronically in the OnLine system. Implementing this system will provide the following benefits:

- through the schedule of work and rest schedule of each vehicle, it is possible

to make quick changes to it through the system;

- puts the drivers in the mode of work balance hours, does not allow tired ones

to work;

- does not tolerate excessive traffic, the line will be filled with the necessary

cars based on the regime, will limit the number of illegally moving cars;

As a result of the analysis of the data obtained, the dynamics of growth shown in our diagram shows the work carried out for the purpose of systemic development in the Republic.

In short, the Republic's "monitoring of the delivery of goods on routes in the network transport system" is a requirement of the times.

By organizing this process, we can have a significant impact on the transport logistics system. We will also determine the prospects for the development of the logistics system.

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